

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

ASD20: a new short-duration rice variety for Tamil Nadu, India

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IR44595-70-2-3-3, a cross-derivative of IR64/IR25863-61-3-2//IR58, was received through the International Rice Testing Program in 1988 and subjected to further selection at RRS. It was designated as AS89044 and released as ASD20 in Jan 1997 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu.

ASD20 is a semidwarf hybrid (89 cm) and matures in 110 d. At this station, it produced a mean yield of 6.7 and 5.6 t ha⁻¹ in dry (June to September) and wet seasons (October to January), respectively. The performance in multi-location, adaptive, minikit, and national trials was good; it registered a mean yield of 5.7 t ha⁻¹ in 320 trials with a 5.6, 9.6, and 9.6% increased yields over ADT36, ASD18, and IR50, respectively (see table). The biological yield of ASD20 is 18.5 t ha⁻¹ (6.7 t ha⁻¹ grain, 11.8 t ha⁻¹ straw) and its potential grain yield is 9.7 t ha⁻¹.

Mean yield performance of ASD20 in different trials. Tamil Nadu, India. 1988-96.

Trial/year	Trials (no.)	Mean grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)					
		ASD20	ADT36	IR50	ASD18	Annada	Tulasi
Station trial							
Dry season (1988-96)	11	6.7	6.2	5.5	5.7	-	-
% increase over checks			8.1	21.2	17.9	-	-
Wet season (1990-91 to 1995-96)	6	5.6	4.5	4.7	4.7	-	-
% increase over check			25.4	19.5	20.4	-	-
Multilocation trial (1991-92)							
% increase over check	19	4.8	-	4.5	4.4	-	-
Adaptive research trial (1992, 1993, and 1996)							
% increase over check	197	5.5	5.4	5.3	5.3	-	-
National trial (1992-94)							
% increase over check	25	5.3	-	-	-	4.5	4.6
Minikit trial							
Overall mean performance	65	6.3	(min range: 3.9-6.1 t ha ⁻¹ ; max range: 6.1-9.1 t ha ⁻¹)				
% increase over check	320	5.7	5.4	5.2	5.2	4.5	4.6
% increase over check			5.6	9.6	9.6	26.7	23.9

ASD20 is resistant to stem borer, leafhopper, and sheath rot and moderately resistant to blast and rice tungro virus. The rice is long, slender, and white with good cooking quality. Protein content (8.0%) is higher than that of IR50 (7.6%). Its milling recovery is

68.5% (IR50 has 66.9%); 1000-grain weight is 22.1 g.

ASD20 is a best alternative to IR50 and suitable for April to July, October to November, and December to January sowings throughout Tamil Nadu, India. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement — flood-prone

Padmanath: an improved deepwater rice in Assam, India

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Deepwater rice varieties in Assam (51-100 cm) are mostly indigenous to the state, require 5-8 mo to mature, encounter occasional droughts and floods up to 3-4 m, and possess genes for stem

elongation and/or submergence tolerance. The average yielding ability of these indigenous types is very low (1.1 t ha⁻¹).

We developed a new deepwater variety, Padmanath, by the bulk pedigree selection method after hybridization among Pankaj/Jagannath//Negheribao. Pankaj and Jagannath are improved high-yielding varieties adapted to waterlogged situations, and Negheribao is a local deepwater rice variety with stem elongation capacity in response to rising water level, tolerating flood up to 3-4 m.

The yield records of Padmanath are presented in the table. The average grain yield was 2.7 t ha⁻¹ over years and locations in the state. Padmanath showed 17% superiority over the check variety Amonabao and 49% over its deepwater rice parent Negheribao. Padmanath was also evaluated in the National Deepwater Rice Yield Trials (PVT 6) during 1989 under the name IET11876, and had 85% submergence survival rate, stem elongation score 3, and yield of 2.6 t ha⁻¹ over Pusa, Chinsurah, Ghagharaghat, and North Lakhimpur as compared with the